

HISTORY OF NATIONAL JEWELRY IN OUR COUNTRY AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE TODAY

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Annotation: *The content of this article is devoted to the study of national jewelry in our country on a scientific and theoretical basis. In particular, the current nationalism in our country is aimed at highlighting the centuries-old history of jewelry, their changes in appearance over the centuries, and their importance today.*

There are several important factors that have preserved the nationalism in the country for centuries, and the appearance of national jewelry as one of them represents the spiritual and cultural heritage, way of thinking and worldview of the people who lived in these periods.

Key words: *national jewels, scientific-theoretical foundations, nationality, centuries-old history, important factors, spiritual-cultural heritage, way of thinking, spiritual forgiveness, worldview, importance.*

Introduction: In the formation of each nation as a nation, there are concepts that reflect its nationality, and to understand how national they are requires a deeper study of nationality. of the nation language with together culture is also today in the day important importance occupation is enough Culture is a nation and him organize doer of society identity and people history, today day and the future meaning concept as showing our passage possible will be

After all, culture if he lives the nation in vain that he lives did not say In this place cultural legacies learning to us not only our history our learning perhaps promising ensuring the future giver important factor is counted.

Jewelry - jewelry in art to be created decoration are items . Jewelry is artistic craftsmanship field; gold, silver, copper, tin such as colorful of metals vegetable items (jewelry) decoration items to make job it is an exaggeration it won't be.¹

Jewellers decoration items in preparation pouring, hammering (forging giving) making, solving (gold and silver water carry out), carve or exaggerated pattern making, printing, linen, sovotkori, mold, mesh such as of methods wide usesю

Tillakosh - jewelry item women's headdress over to the forehead wearable is a jewel. Gold or gold water run silver and another of metals is made. Tillakosh basis don't cry eyebrow shaped each other with 2 parts that connect harvest does, fragments connected to the place one piece mute pinned, pieces surface patterns with decorated, high

edge turquoise eyes with framed; don't cry eyebrow of form to the top fenced patterns is processed and triangle shaped crown apparently have will be, with a grid flowers to the middle turquoise eyes with framed necklace and another steps is installed.

Pray lower to the part mutual alternately coming small bead and petals typed one short, one long chains hangs. Also his high part of the center (tip) and two from the edge chains they are taken out in the center unite and hook with will be completed. One different

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zargarlik>

artistic method decorated love gajak, isirga, zebigardon with together ensemble harvest does.

Tillakosh to the shape similar to the forehead wearable ornament item Fergona in the valley leaf, upper part fenced patterns didn't happen type In Bukhara, it is also called of Khorezm asthma jewelry to himself special decoration with from tillakosh difference does from long ago daughter in law and young women the function of a protective amulet done. Tillakosh now, mostly, wedding in the ceremony and of dancers national of his dress structural part as is used.

To us as you know, our country for jewelry art Uzbek national, artistic culture of history indispensable part being is coming Jewelry of art a lot century traditions and values recovery and him more fundamentally improvement, field in the system work release activity efficiency increase for comfortable infrastructure Create in order to President by May 18, 2019 "Uzbekistan in the Republic jewelry network fast development measures on"² Decree No. PF-5721 acceptance done.

This is it decree because of in the country jewelry networks again organize reach and them more development as well work to the producers precious of metals use the right given, local jewelry products size expansion the ground created. Also this decree with in the field systematic of shortcomings existence recognition done without investments active attraction to make, quality jewelry products work release according to activity walking powers modernization to do and new ones organize reach, this products export to expand hindrance so, the network development negative influence showing to factors check was put

Craftsmen association member, jeweler Alzar Boboyev jewelry history about interesting data according to lecture and

² <https://lex.uz/docs/-4344351?otherlang=1> Uzbekistan Republic "Uzbekistan in the Republic jewelry network fast development measures on" Decree No. PF-5721.

jewelry to make master class from the process past gave.³

Craftsman's to his words According to Uzbek national jewelry of the school based on Bukhara template lies _ India and Iran under the influence of the most first developed Bukhara in jewelry small stones, elegant and soft of ornaments used if so, to the 16th century come form started Tashkent, valley in jewelry making big stones and big patterns to use superiority did.

At the exhibition not only jewelry accessories - necklace, necklace, bracelet the like, perhaps hand to work based on sozana, clothes - head, khontakta such as own of the era life style about story doer also watch the accessories to do can.

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Hat just a headdress being no more, him

³ <https://kun.uz/uz/59504647?q=%2Fuz%2F59504647> From Zebigardon until the end: "Lifelong jewelry" exhibition being is passing January 31 – International jewelry day relationship with practical art and craftsmanship history state in the museum "Lifelong jewelry" exhibition the work started. In it to the last XIX - XX centuries relevant, Tashkent, Khorezm, Bukhara, Fergana jewelry to the original appearance of schools have samples demonstration is being done.

wore person's social status also information about gave. An example for, to marry did not come out girls silk hat wore if he is married young people dice from the ball used. "Every one of the area hat pattern too with from each other difference will do" he said story does guide-expert.

Khakimjon Shodmonov information according to the museum 8 thousand in the fund near exhibit there is and 600 of them are jewelry items is considered Most the exhibit belongs to the 19th century.

Above given feedback that's it shows that Uzbek national jewelry with together national reflection bringer national clothes are also available being they are centuries during his own value save is coming Har one of the nation today's of the day promising the future providing gave national culture years during forming to go exactly nationality more deep realize reach is also related to.

This historical and national jewelry our country for spiritual and cultural and educational importance as follows our show possible will be:

- spirituality right in formation in history important traditions and values meaning to stand;
- cultural our heritages learning through promising our future sure set get opportunity creation;
- national jewelry is historical heritage being, him learning through of our ancestors original goals our understanding possible will be;
- young generation how education under formation practical assistance;
- religious tolerance and international harmony in strengthening nationality reflection bringer jewelry spiritual effect to show;
- of our culture complete formation help giver national of jewelry centuries during own appearance without losing today's of the day jewelry of items to the creation basis to be;
- young generation perfect and healthy in the spirit education in doing national in itself liberating of legacies research to be done provide;

Summary in place that's it note reach that's right, in our republic this about there is national sweets learning and they are on research their work take them away more deep learning through in the past spiritual and cultural tradition and our values our understanding possible will be Also jewelry industry in perspective Central in Asia the most leader work issuer from fields to one to convert must will be.

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